

METHOD OF TEACHING THE CLARINET TO BEGINNERS

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Annotation: This article provides guidelines for teaching students to play the clarinet.

Key words: clarinet, wind instruments, music lessons, methodology, teacher, educational process.

The method of learning to play a musical instrument is part of musical pedagogy. Based on the analysis and generalization of the experience of the best domestic and foreign teachers - musicians and performers, the methodology studies the patterns and techniques of individual learning. The method of teaching wind instruments is perhaps the "youngest" among other performing methods, it took shape and developed gradually. Each generation of musicians has contributed to its development.

Tool varieties.

At the end of the seventeenth century, presumably in 1690, Pogan Christoph Denner (1655 - 1707), an outstanding musical master of woodwind instruments from Nuremberg, invented a new instrument, a modified chalumeau, which was the prototype of the modern clarinet, it was unusual that instead of an incised tongue, which was a characteristic detail many types of chalumeau, a beak-shaped wooden mouthpiece with a reed cane appeared on the new instrument, which was tied to the mouthpiece with a cord. The first clarinet was only fifty centimeters long (general tuning in C), it had eight open sound holes, of which one was located on the back and closed with the thumb of the left hand, and two valves.

Instrumental masters of the past, in the process of consistently improving the designs of the in B clarinet, created a number of varieties of this instrument. Modern opera, symphony and wind orchestras use: soprano clarinets C - flat, A, small clarinets E - flat, C and bass clarinet, which allows composers to use combinations of various clarinet timbres in their works.

The modern clarinet (Böhm's systems) is a completely perfect instrument with good timbre qualities in all registers and sufficient intonation accuracy of sounds. The valve mechanism of this instrument is designed very expediently, thanks to which it is more convenient and easier to play the Boehm system clarinet (French) than the Oehler system clarinet (German). Boehm's system clarinets have significant differences in the construction of some parts of the

valve-lever mechanism, which is primarily due to the characteristic principle of playing the use of the little fingers. If, when playing the clarinet of the Oehler system, each of the little fingers of the performer usually presses two adjacent valves and does this with the help of sliding movements on special rollers, then for the clarinets of the Boehm system, instead of "sliding" transitions, the principle of alternate movement of both little fingers is used, each of which controls the movements of four interchangeable valves. This principle of movement is more convenient and efficient, and provides the performers with the most favorable conditions for the development of finger technique.

A beginner in learning to play the clarinet should not use an instrument that has any significant shortcomings, because in an effort to overcome them and adapt to a defective instrument, the student may acquire some incorrect skills that will interfere with his normal development.

Student selection.

The selection of students should be treated with great attention and high demands. The most experienced and talented teacher will be doomed to failure in his pedagogical work if his students do not have sufficient professional data. An attempt to develop weak abilities, as a rule, does not justify the effort expended.

Not being in any way a harmful profession, playing the clarinet should be contraindicated for persons suffering from any form of lung and heart disease. Therefore, only those who have passed the medical examination with satisfactory results should be admitted to admission tests. Speaking about the physical features that interfere with learning to play the clarinet, you need to keep in mind only deviations from the norm. Minor physical defects like, for example, a slight curvature of the front teeth in a number of cases did not prevent talented people from achieving a high degree of skill.

The decisive criterion in determining the suitability of an applicant to study the clarinet should be sufficient musicality: a good ear for music, a sense of rhythm and musical memory. Careful verification of these data by the student is essential. The most favorable age at which one should start learning to play the clarinet is nine, ten years old. At this time, the whole organism reaches the already necessary development, and training can go very well, at a later age one usually has to face difficulties, mainly in improving technique. A prerequisite for the normal development of a clarinetist is a performance that meets the following requirements: you must stand straight, your legs can be slightly apart. Hands should not be tense and pressed to the body. Fingers slightly bent lie

freely on the valves. The tool is supported on a stand with the thumb of the right hand. The reed with the mouthpiece should lie in the middle of the lower lip, the corners of the mouth tightly closed, the upper teeth touching the mouthpiece at a distance of about two-thirds from the cut.

The first stage of teaching a beginner requires a lot of attention from the teacher. It is necessary to monitor the correct position of the instrument, and breathing, and the accuracy of intonation, and all performing movements. The slightest oversight of the teacher can lead to the assimilation of incorrect skills by the student, the correction of which always presents significant difficulties. The most useful remarks and instructions of the teacher will not give significant results if the student himself does not understand that each instruction of the teacher is a task for persistent, systematic, independent homework, without which it is impossible to achieve success.

It should be noted the most common shortcomings found in beginner clarinetists who underwent initial training with poor or inexperienced teachers:

- ❖ Incorrect position of the hands - they are unnaturally curved inward, thereby reducing the mobility of the fingers.
- ❖ Cheeks and lips are inflated during the game, while violating the setting of the labial apparatus, which entails a distortion of the sound, its intonational instability.
- ❖ Highly raised during the game and protruding free fingers should also be considered a significant drawback that limits the technique and spoils the appearance of the player.
- ❖ Incorrect set of breathing "in the chest" does not allow to produce a full set of air, limiting the performing tasks.

To eliminate and prevent the appearance of these and other possible shortcomings, the teacher needs not only great attention in the initial period of training, but also perseverance and perseverance in the struggle for the quality of the production.

A beginner to learn to play the clarinet should practice at least two or three times a day, since the duration of each lesson should not exceed twenty minutes. In the initial period of training, the main attention of the teacher should be focused on the quality of the sound. From the very first lessons, it is necessary to develop in students a high demand for the beauty of the sound of the instrument and the purity of intonation, otherwise the student will get used to the shortcomings of his sound and inaccurate intonation, ceasing to improve these most important aspects of his performing skills.

Physiological characteristics of the performing process.

The art of playing the clarinet, as well as any other wind instrument, can certainly be attributed to one of the most difficult types of human labor activity, since in the process of musical performance, the clarinet player must very accurately coordinate the actions of a number of components: vision, hearing, memory, thinking, respiratory apparatus, muscle-motor skills associated with the work of the lips, tongue, fingers, volitional efforts, musical and aesthetic ideas, etc.

It is this variety of psycho-physiological actions performed by the musician in the process of playing that determines the complexity of the musical performance technique. The decisive role in this complex process belongs to the performer's mind, that is, his conscious attitude to performance issues and deliberate actions in order to achieve the intended artistic task.

The process of sound extraction on the clarinet can be imagined as several interconnected links of a single psycho-physiological chain: a musical sign - an idea of sound - a muscular-motor system - a performing movement - a real sound - auditory analysis. During the implementation of this relationship, the central place belongs to the musical and auditory sensations and ideas of the player. Relying on his inner hearing, the ability for musical and auditory imagination, the performer, in the process of playing the instrument, constantly embodies the previously internally heard sounds into real sounds. This is the most important feature of any musical performance.

The first group should include strokes performed with a solid sound attack:

- Detache - characterized by an energetic, but not sharp push of the tongue during an attack and a fairly full length of the sound.
- Markato - a technique for extracting separate, emphasized strong sounds with an accentuated beginning of the sound and its subsequent weakening.
- Staccato - the extraction of individual, jerky sounds with the help of quick and light tongue thrusts.
- Martel - extraction of individual, emphasized and sustained sounds on the same speaker with the help of an energetic attack and enhanced exhalation.
- Tenuto - a technique for extracting separate, clear, but not accentuated, extremely sustained sounds in duration.

The second group will include strokes performed by a soft sound attack:

1. Non legato - a technique for extracting slightly shortened individual sounds with a soft push of the tongue during an attack.
2. Portato - the extraction of sounds with the help of soft, imperceptible jolts of the tongue during an attack, providing a smooth transition from sound to sound while maintaining their duration as much as possible.
3. Legato - connected extraction of sounds, in which the tongue is involved only in the reproduction of the first sound;

The third group consists of the most complex and specific methods of performance, requiring special articulation techniques, these include:

1. Double staccato;
2. Frou plateau;
3. Glissando;

The skills of performing strokes and their continuous improvement should be instilled in clarinetists from the first steps of learning to play the clarinet. In this case, the study of various strokes should take place in a certain sequence. In the beginning, you should study the simplest strokes (detache, legato), and then move on to mastering more complex and specific strokes.

Conclusion.

Modern clarinet performance imposes broad and varied requirements on the player: to be confident in all types of musical technique, to be able to aesthetically comprehend the game, to have active thinking, a rich and diverse emotional sphere. All this is intended to serve a single goal - the achievement of maximum expressiveness and persuasiveness of musical performance, carried out with the help of a complex of various expressive performing means. The problems raised here have been raised by domestic teachers and performers for a long time and I would like to believe that someday they will still be resolved.

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